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Modern Football and Main Directions in Scientific Research Issues of Students

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***Annotation:** In order to determine the main directions of scientific research, it is necessary to have a clear idea of the development trends of modern football and whether training loads correspond to game loads.*

***Key words:** Modern football, players, result, central striker, perfection of passing, physical training. The development process is intense, judging by the games of the last world championships.*

In game tactics:

The organization of fast attacks along the width and length of the field is used. The actions of the defensive line players, the midfield players in the rapid organization of dense defense, and, if necessary, the participation of the attackers in organizing these actions;

In the tactical actions of group pressing against opponents moving with the ball in different parts of the field, the importance of the coordinated actions of the players is increasing;

The importance of skilled players "stars" in achieving the final result of the game is increasing;

The importance of group quick actions, carried out with the active participation of 5-6 players in attack and defense, has sharply increased;

It is still important to organize the "arrhythmia" of the game: alternating high game pace with pauses;

The game becomes more active with clearly manifested pressing elements.

In the attacking phases:

The relevance of the role of the central striker in different phases of the attack, the ability to foresee, strong athletic training, excellent ball control technique in difficult conditions of struggle with defenders, perfection of deceiving and hitting the goal with the foot;

Participation in pressing actions in the fight for the ball in front of the opponent's field in a situation where the ball is lost, returning, participating in group actions in the fight for the ball in the second zone (midfield zone) and, if necessary, in the first zone;

The ability to create free zones for partners to organize an attack with their own quick movements;

Fast and accurate passing of the ball by players participating in the attack over short and medium distances. Delivering the ball to partners in one or two touches even when a large number of forwards are concentrated in certain parts of the field;

The importance of defenders and wing midfielders is increasing. Maximum use of wing attacks. The tendency to effectively use powerful diagonal and wing passes in the zones in front of the near and far posts of the goal;

Maximum use of positional errors of defenders playing in a linear defense and bringing one of the attackers to the free zone in front of the goal using the "wall" method;

Maximum use of good opportunities arising from the implementation of standard situations;

High level of heading in defense and attack.

In the defensive phases:

Organizing the first line of defense. It refers to the actions of the attackers after losing the ball in the opponent's field (pressing the defender moving with the ball);

Second line of defense: dense, lined, i.e. "linear" placement of players in front of the center line of the field (the optimal distance between players is 7-8 meters);

Third line of defense: "linear" placement of players (20-30 meters to the "goal"). As you approach your own goal, switch to a personal pursuit method: the distance between the second and third line defenders should be 10-12 meters, but this distance can change depending on the game conditions;

The "linear" placement of the defense and midfield players is a very important factor in the tactics of pressing the opponent moving with the ball. Game technique:

- putting the ball into play is simple and reliable;
- the power of the blow and accuracy when passing the ball to partners have increased;
- speed and purposefulness of movements are decisive in the final stage of the attack;

Various types of movements are observed when hitting the ball (on tiptoe, on the chest); feints and deceptive movements are still widely used;

Complete abandonment of the style of playing by stopping the ball: the ball is controlled in motion and attempts to outwit the opponent are made;

The development of technical movements and fast techniques continues in certain limited parts of the football field.

Physical training.

- the relevance of developing speed-strength qualities and speed endurance;
- developing agility and flexibility for effective control of game activity;
- cultivating the speed, rhythm and agility necessary in the fight against the opponent;

- Ensuring a constant increase in the team's game potential. The following can serve as methods of scientific research work of students of the Institute of Physical Education:

Working with literature.

It is clear that the researcher will rely on the body of knowledge acquired at previous stages of development on this issue. Working with scientific literature or newspaper articles is a component of this research activity. At this stage of the work, a specific topic is selected and the objectives and idea of the research are determined, the hypothesis of the scientific work is developed and the methods are determined. A systematic and comprehensive study of the literature on the topic being studied is an indispensable condition for scientific activity.

The student must know the following:

The importance of working with literature and other types of published materials;

The importance of searching for the necessary literature and preliminary acquaintance with them;

The importance of using materials from the literature in the research process and systematizing them.

Analysis of the work experience of trainers. Interviews and their research functions are widely known in pedagogical practice. It is a source of information and can be combined with other psychological and pedagogical research methods: observation, laboratory and natural experiments, questionnaires, analysis of training activities, etc. The effectiveness of the interview, as a rule, also depends on the qualifications of the researcher, his psychological preparation, level of theoretical knowledge, the art of conducting an interview, and his personal appearance. The interviewees should not be aware of the true purpose of the study, as inaccuracies may be observed in the answers. When preparing for the interview, it is necessary to determine in advance the purpose and content of the research interview, as well as the methods of recording the results of the interview (dictaphone, stenography). Currently, the use of the questionnaire method is widespread in psychological and pedagogical research. This method has many similarities with the interview method. In both methods, questions are used and answers are obtained. Personal communication is not required for the questionnaire, it can be sent by mail or other method. The questionnaire method does not require great skill. The students themselves can be active participants in the questionnaire questions and answers.

When studying the work experience of tutors, the student should know the following:

The importance of the research function of the interview with the object;

The importance of the questionnaire questions and answers in research;

Observation as a pedagogical research method.

Knowledge of professional observation is important for every coach. Despite its seeming simplicity, research observations in games and training sessions have certain difficulties and their own stages of development.

Students are advised to use simple pedagogical observation cards when conducting research, for example, to study the dependence of the quality of the training process of young football players on accurate passing of the ball in games.

Depending on the goals and objectives of the research, other types of pedagogical cards are used, for example, to determine the amount of distance traveled.

As the researcher's qualifications increase, more complex pedagogical observation cards are developed. To complete them, new, relatively advanced equipment or technical observation tools are required.

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